

Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel(II) with Salicylaldehyde-Guanyldiazone

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Manuscript received 16 July 1990, revised 1 September 1992, accepted 21 September 1992

Guanyldiazones form complexes with transition metal ions. Aldehyde and ketone give easily crystallisable guanyldiazone derivatives, which were first synthesised by Thiele and Dralle¹.

The present authors have noted that the aqueous solution of salicylaldehyde guanyldiazone (SAG) gives an yellow coloured complex with Ni^{II} in alkaline medium, which leads to the development of a simple and rapid spectrophotometric method for the determination of nickel.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of complex [Ni^{II}-SAG] recorded at pH 9.52, shows absorption maximum at 370 nm, where the reagent solution has no significant absorption. The molar extinction coefficient at 370 nm is $1.0563 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The complex is stable after 15 min.

The absorbance between pH 8.5 and 10.5 was found constant and maximum. Hence spectral measurements were done at pH 9.52. The colour of the complex was stable over several hours. A four-fold excess of the reagent was sufficient for full colour development.

The Beer's law is valid upto 5 ppm. The optimum concentration range of nickel, determined from the Ringbom plot², was found to be 3.15–4.75 ppm and Sandell sensitivity³ $0.03907 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

The composition of the complex as determined by Job's method of continuous variation² and mole ratio method⁵, was found to be 1:2 (Ni : SAG).

The degree of dissociation⁶ was found to be 0.0877 and the apparent instability constant⁷ of the complex was 8.595×10^{-13} . The change in free energy⁸ of the system is $-16.453 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

A number of ions were examined for their interference in the determination of nickel by the

recommended procedure. Deviation of not more than $\pm 3\%$ from the expected absorbance was taken as the standard tolerance limit for the system. Interference of Fe and Mn^{II} can be eliminated by fluoride. Ag^I was masked with 0.1% thiourea solution (2 ml) and Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} with 5% sodium thiosulphate solution (2 ml). Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, Cr^{VI}, Co^{II}, V^{IV}, citrate and EDTA interfered seriously. The tolerance limits of W^{VI}, thiourea and urea were 275.0, 400.0 and 600.0 ppm respectively.

The proposed method is reproducible, simple and rapid. It was tested by analysing solution containing a known amount of nickel. The average of five determinations of 20 μg nickel was found to be 19.48 μg with a relative mean deviation of $\pm 1.14\%$.

To assess the validity of the method it was applied for the determination of nickel in alloy steel by proper masking of Fe, Mn and Cu. The recovery was found to be $\sim 97\%$.

Experimental

The spectral measurements were done on a Baush and Lomb Spectronic-20 instrument. The pH measurements were done on an Elico pH meter using glass-calomel combination electrode and standard phthalate (pH=4.01) and borax (pH=9.18) buffers were used for the standardisation.

Aminoguanidine bicarbonate (2.0 g) was completely dissolved in concentrated HNO₃ (till evolution of CO₂ ceased) and salicylaldehyde (1.793 g, 1.54 ml) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) was added to it. The mixture was kept as such for 0.5 h. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol as shining white crystals of salicylaldehyde guanyldiazone (SAG) ($\sim 1.8 \text{ g}$), m.p. 209–10° (Found : C, 53.69 ; H, 5.87 ; N, 30.96. C₈H₁₀N₄O requires : C, 53.94 ; H, 5.61 ; N, 31.47%).

The reagent SAG was found soluble in water, ethanol, methanol and acetone but insoluble in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and benzene. The ionisation constant of the reagent was obtained both by spectrophotometric and by pH-metric methods. The pK value was found to be 10.7.

A stock solution of SAG (0.01 mol) was prepared in distilled water. A stock solution containing

1 mg ml⁻¹ nickel was prepared by dissolving nickel chloride hexahydrate (A.R.) in distilled water containing little concentrated HCl and was standardised gravimetrically by dimethylglyoxime method⁹; the working solution was prepared by appropriate dilution.

The buffer solution was prepared by mixing appropriate amount of borax and NaOH.

General procedure: To an aliquot of the solution containing about 10 µg of Ni^{II} was added 0.6 ml of the reagent (SAG) solution (1.0 × 10⁻³ M), pH of the solution was adjusted to 9.52 by adding borax buffer solution (1.0 ml) and made upto 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 370 nm against the reagent blank. The concentration of nickel was determined from a calibration curve.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities of the Shivaji University. One of them (R.V.N.)

thanks U.G.C., New Delhi, authorities of Phaltan Education Society, Phaltan, and Principal, Mudhoji College, Phaltan.

References

1. J. THIELE and E. DRALLE, *Ann.*, 1898, 302, 278.
2. L. MERTIS, "Handbook of Analytical Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1963, pp. 6-17.
3. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 84.
4. P. JOB, *Compt. Rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, 9, 113.
5. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
6. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
7. K. C. TRIKHA, M. KATYAL and R. P. SINGH, *Talanta*, 1967, 14, 977.
8. A. A. GRINBERG, "An Introduction to the Chemistry of Complex Compounds", Translated by J. R. Leach, Pergamon, London, 1962, p. 275.
9. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1968, p. 480.